

Xiaojing "Classic of Filial Piety"

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Throughout the history of imperial China, members of the political elite have held the Xiaojing 孝經 (Classic of Filial Piety) in high esteem. During the Eastern Han (A.D. 25-220), every government school had a lecturer on this text. Emperors often expounded on the classic, ordered that commentaries be written for it, and had the scripture engraved in stone. One emperor, Emperor Tang Xuanzong 唐玄宗 (r. 712-756), even penned a commentary on it himself. During the Northern Song 北宋 (960-1127), the dynasty's two greatest statesmen, Wang Anshi 王安石 (1021-1086) and Sima Guang 司馬光 (1019-1086), who were enemies, each wrote a treatise favoring a different version of the text. When northerners conquered China, the Xiaojing was one of the first books they translated into their native language. The Xiaojing quickly made its way to Japan, Korea, and Vietnam, where it became essential reading for the upper class. Ironically, two of the features that made the Xiaojing philosophically shallow, but culturally important were its brevity and simplicity. It is only 1800 Chinese characters long; moreover, it repeatedly uses the same 388 characters. Thus, one merely had to learn 400 characters to be able to read the text. This meant that it was very easy to learn and memorize, which made it one of the first texts that a student would read in trying to master the classical language. This guaranteed that the Xiaojing was widely known and easily distributed. Its simple language also meant that it could serve as both a primer and a catechism. Hence, in medieval China, the Xiaojing was the first true book that a student would study. In fact, in pre-modern East Asia, nearly any person who was educated in literary Chinese was almost certainly familiar with this text. During the Tang (618-907) and the Northern Song (960-1127), civil service examination candidates had to study this work. From the Southern Song (1127-1279), the text lost its valence among male members of the upper class; instead, it was used to educate children, women, and farmers. In the late Ming (1368-1643), it once again found importance among male literati, particularly thinkers who emphasized the unity of the Three Religions (Sanjiao he yi 三教合一). These men emphasized the work's religious aspects, especially its abilities to bring about response from the spirits (gantong shenming 感通神明). During the Qing (1644-1911), the Xiaojing once again came into vogue and became a text that had to be memorized for taking the civil service examinations. Given its title, one would expect the text to say much about what it is and how one should practice filiality. Interestingly though, the Xiaojing says little about the particulars of being filial. Clearly then, it was not meant as a handbook on the practice of this virtue. The Xiaojing's most significant insight is that one's obligations to the family and the state are the same and not mutually exclusive. In other words, the Xiaojing attempts to resolve the dilemma between whether one should be loyal to his family or the state. It does so by unequivocally maintaining that no such conflict exists. That is because filial sons cannot but be loyal retainers. The text stakes this claim on three ideas: 1. That filiality naturally becomes loyalty. 2. Sons can only complete their filiality by serving as officials. And 3. how one acts in the home will automatically become how one acts within the state. Another way in which the text indicates that a son must be a loyal servitor is by maintaining that official service is needed to complete filiality. Taking care of one's parents, when they are alive and after their death, is critically important; nevertheless, according to the Xiaojing, these acts still do not completely realize filiality. That can only be done by glorifying their memory. The best way to do this is by perfecting one's conduct and serving in public office. Serving in government is a surefire way of bringing honor to their names. Another significant theme that the Xiaojing advocates is filiality's metaphysical significance. According to the text, filial piety is not merely one amongst many virtues. It is the foundational virtue from which all others issue. Even more importantly, it is not merely a secular virtue: it is a metaphysical principle that links people with Heaven and Earth, i.e. the universe. In short, due to filiality's metaphysical importance, if a ruler devotes his attention to it, he can gain supernatural protection for both his person and his state. Consequently, during the early medieval period and the late Ming, the Xiaojing was a holy text that could be used to cure illnesses, obtain religious merit, repel evil spirits, and even enemy armies.

– Incised or Inscribed

↳ Method of inscription

– Chisel

Notes: The Xiaojing was often carved into stone stele, particularly at imperial universities.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Wood

↳ Species

– Specify: I don't know

– Bamboo

– Stone

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: I do not know.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: I do not know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: I do not know.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: Since it was a Confucian classic, among other places, it would have been stored at schools and Confucian temples. These places often had statues of Confucius and his seventy-two disciples, and murals of outstanding officials and generals.

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Some public spaces

Notes: The *Xiao jing* could be found at court, in government yamens (offices), schools, and of course at Confucian temples. All of those places might have had illustrations of

Confucius and his disciples, and or illustrations of Confucian exemplars.

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Confucian iconography often features auspicious creatures that become manifest because of exemplary human actions. These auspicious beasts often adorned the walls of tombs. Images of these beasts were often collected in books and presented to the emperor.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: In a number of Confucian filial piety tales gods or goddesses are depicted. They are always human in form. They are often heavenly deities. The most famous is the Weaving Maiden who descends down to the world to help the filial son Dong Yong 董永 pay off his debt.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes there will be illustrations of famous passages. For example, on some artifacts have images of the phrase "As if we were approaching a deep abyss; as if we treading on thin ice" 如臨深淵、如履薄冰 from the hallowed classic the Book of Poetry 詩經. It means that one should be careful in all endeavors. Sometimes the Classics themselves were illustrated, such as the Book of Odes and the Xiaojing.

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Confucian iconography is appropriately largely concentrated on humans, the most important of whom is Confucius. Most often Confucius is depicted together with his disciples. Until the 1530 reform of rituals, Confucian temples included statues of Confucius and a number of his most important disciples. Even after the reform, the most important temple to Confucius in Qufu (Confucius' birthplace) still had icons. Palaces oftentimes had images of meritorious officials on the walls of certain halls. Beyond the court, many localities had shrines with images of meritorious officials who had served there. In the late imperial period, private academies would have images of the founders of Neo-Confucianism. There were also images of exemplars who perfectly realized Confucian virtues. Images of famous filial sons and outstanding women decorated lacquered screens and plates, as well as the funerary furniture and tombs walls of the dead. Illustrated versions of books such as the *Accounts of Outstanding Women* (Lienü zhuan 列女傳), *Accounts of Filial Offspring* (Xiaozi zhuan 孝子傳), and the *Twenty-four Filial Exemplars* (Ershisi xiao 二十四孝) circulated widely. In late imperial times, there were also portraits and sculptures of ancestors that would be venerated during holidays connected with the ancestral rites. This practice might date even earlier: the Eastern Han dynasty story of the filial exemplar Ding Lan 丁蘭 tells us that, after his parent died, he made an image out of wood of his parent and treated it as if it were alive.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

Notes: There was not supernatural narratives per se. However, in narratives about filial sons and daughters oftentimes include supernatural content, such as miracles. A common late imperial image of the filial son Dong Yong shows his goddess wife rising to the sky on a cloud. The story of Guo Ju 郭巨 who wants to bury his infant son alive so he can make sure his elderly mother has sufficient food always features a cauldron filled with gold that Heaven has awarded him for his filial heart.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: The most common type of illustrated Confucian narrative people would be exposed to are tales of filial exemplars. The *Twenty-four Filial Exemplars* books were usually illustrated and given to children. Christian missionaries of the 19th and 20th centuries tell us that, if a family had one book, it was the *Twenty-four Filial Exemplars*. In late imperial China, there were also pictorial biographies of Confucius, which were called *Pictures of the Sage's Traces* (Shengji tu 聖跡圖). Of course, there were also illustrated versions of the *Accounts of Outstanding Women*.

↳ Specify

–Specify: No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: For most of the imperial period, the answer is no. However, after the ritual reform of 1530, icons of Confucius and his disciples were replaced by spirit tablets, which were merely wooden tablets with the revered person's name and title. This happened because the Jiaqing Emperor and other reformers believed that images of deities came from Buddhist influence, the gods were unfathomable, and images were uncanonical.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Of course the state often sponsored editions of the Xiaojing, but most copies were produced by private individuals in the manuscript age and then by printing presses in late imperial China.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, because the emperor was both the head of the state and the chief officiant of the state religion, which was Confucianism.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, when the Xiaojing was carved onto a stele at the imperial university, officials would have been involved in the process. When Emperor Tang Xuanzong 唐玄宗 (r. 713-756) annotated the Xiaojing, he ordered it to be distributed to official schools across the empire. This distribution would have required the efforts of many officials in charge of education. Song Taizong 宋太宗 (r. 975-998) authorized a second imperial edition with commentary, which was carried out by Xing Bing 邢昺 932-1010). Finally, the Kangxi 康熙 emperor of the Qing ordered his officials to extensively annotate the text. It became the 100 chapter Imperially Produced Extended Explanation of the Classic of Filial Piety (Yuding Xiaojing yanyi 御定孝經衍義). It was distributed to all of the empire's provinces in 1690. Both the production and distribution of the text would have required the efforts of scores of officials.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, if the emperor or local magistrate felt that a person was unfilial, he might hand the culprit a copy of the Xiaojing and urge him to take its teachings to heart.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– No

Notes: This simple text could be copied by anyone with a modicum of education. Nevertheless, in early imperial China, at the imperial university, an erudite who was a master of this text was appointed. It would have been such a man who directed the text of the class that would be carved on a stele at the imperial university.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: Since the Xiaojing was commonly used as a primer, in imperial China it was often recited in school settings. Students would first learn how to recite the text and would only gradually be taught what it means. At certain periods, it was also recited as a religious text, particularly during the Eastern Han (25-220), Six Dynasties (220-589), and the late Ming (1368-1644).

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the historical period, but there were times where Confucius was viewed as a semi-divine being, particularly during the Han Dynasty (206 BCE - 220 CE).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: In its first sentence, the Xiaojing gives us its origin story: " Once when Confucius was at rest and Zengzi was waiting on him, Confucius said, "....". That is that the book

was a lecture by Confucius that was given to his student Zengzi who happened to be Confucius' disciple who was most famous for his filial behavior. Most imperial era Chinese thus believed the book was authored either by Confucius, or Zengzi who wrote down his master's lecture. Hence, part of the text's substantial importance was that it was believed one of the two classics authored by Confucius -- the other being the *Spring and Autumn Annals*. Many late imperial scholars thought it had been created by neither Confucius nor Zengzi, but by one of Zengzi's disciples. Modern scholars not only doubt that either Confucius or Zengzi authored the text, but also that it was jotted down by one of Zengzi's disciples. They believe a Confucian scholar either created it in the late Warring States (481-206 BCE) or the Western Han (206 BCE - 8 CE).

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: However, there were two versions of the text, the New Text version and the Old Text version. During the reign of the First Emperor of the Qin, he had most books burned. Hence, once the Qin fell, scholars had to recall the text by memory. This was called the New Text; it had eighteen sections. Later, when a wall was torn down in the home of Confucius, another slightly different version of the text was found, which was divided into twenty sections. This was called the Old Text version.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: Individual scholars could transmit their own interpretation of the text. The historian Ban Gu said that in his time there were five different schools of interpretation of the text.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

Notes: Individual scholars were free to come up with their own interpretations, which they would write down in their commentaries. During the early medieval period (220-589), there were over 50 different interpretations of the text.

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: There was a huge division between those scholars who championed the Zheng commentary on the New Text version, while others favored the Kong Anguo commentary of the Ancient text version.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– Yes

Notes: This is more of a yes and no question. From time to time, the emperor would convene scholars meetings of scholars to sort out the differences in the interpretation of canonical texts. For example, in 719, Tang Xuanzong (r. 713-755) convened a meeting to determine which Xiaojing commentary was better: the New Text Zheng

commentary, or the Kong Anguo Old Text. The scholars couldn't come to an agreement, so both commentaries were allowed to circulate. However, Xuanzong came up with his own commentary to the text and had that widely distributed throughout the empire.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

Notes: Individual scholars could put forward their own interpretation of the text. By the Tang Dynasty, there were two interpretations of the text. Zheng's commentary on the New Text Xiaojing (which some thought was penned by the famous scholar Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 (127-200), and Kong Anguo's commentary on the Old Text Xiao Jing.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: The individual classics could not be altered; however, how many books were classics could change. The core classics are known as the Five Classics (the Wujing 五經): Book of Poetry Shijing 詩經, the Book of Changes yijing 易經, the Record of Rituals (Li ji 禮記), and the Spring and Autumn Annals (Chunqiu 春秋). In the Eastern Han (25-220), both the _Analects_ (Lunyu 論語) and the _Xiaojing_ were incorporated into the canon to make the Seven Classics (Qijing 七經). During the Tang, this number was raised to twelve, and by the Song, there were thirteen classics.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Notes: Yes the Thirteen Classics (Shisanjing 十三經), include the three supposed commentaries to the Spring and Autumn Annals. These are the Zuozhuan 左傳, the Gongyang zhuan 公羊傳, and the Guliang zhuan 穀梁傳.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to say and depends on when we are talking about. In early imperial China (221 BCE - 906 CE), the primary people reading it was the upper-class, along with some literate commoners. By the late imperial period, particularly the Qing (1644-1911), nearly everyone who had some modicum of learning had read the _Xiaojing_. The text served as a primer for women and children, a morality book for the religiously minded, and for scholars a classic that had to be studied.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
 - No
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Since most people were first exposed to the Xiaojing as a text book, most people absorbed its ideas through learning how to read the text.
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
 - No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: During the early medieval period, the *_Xiaojing_* was often recited because of its supposed magical powers. It was thought that through recitation of the text one could keep evil at bay and beckon good fortune. It was also believed that it could cure illnesses. One unlucky local official even thought its recitation could repel invaders. Perhaps because it was believed to have apotropaic power, some early medieval literati asked that the *_Xiaojing_* should be buried with them. During the Northern Song (960-1127), literati often recited the text while they were mourning their parents. They did this in part to refute the notion that Buddhist

sutras should be read while mourning one's parents. Some late Ming (1368-1644) and the early Qing (1644-1911) also devoted themselves to ritual recitation of the text.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?
– No

↳ Is it read?
– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?
– Yes

Notes: Although it is not directly stated, I would think the effect of repeatedly reciting the text, like one would a Buddhist sutra, would be to make oneself more filial. Huangfu Mi (215-282) asked that he be buried with the Xiaojing to demonstrate that he would never forget filial piety. In other words, by being mindful of filiality, you are filial.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?
– Yes

Notes: In the Northern Song, when a filial son was reciting the Xiaojing while mourning his parent, he appears to have been demonstrating that he was different from others in that he was not reciting Buddhist scriptures. Nevertheless, since he was reciting a holy book before his beloved dead, one would think he was doing so to help them transition to the afterlife. In other words, reciting the _Xiaojing_ at funerals probably had the same purpose as reciting the _Guanyin jing_ at funerals. When early medieval men recited the _Xiaojing_, they hoped it would move the gods of Heaven and Earth to help them cure illnesses, fend off demons, or stop rebellions.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: When he was only five years old, everytime Cen Zhijing 岑之敬 (sixth century), read aloud the _Xiaojing_, he would burn incense and sit properly. When his father was ill, for three days and three nights, kneeling, Xu Fen 徐份 burned incense and recited the _Xiaojing_. Sun Jie 孫介 (1114-1188) recited the _Xiaojing_ every morning. Lu Weiqi 呂維祺 (1587-1641) habitually recited the _Xiaojing_ for over 20 years. Each morning, Yang Qiyuan 楊起元 (1547-1599) would cleanse himself, wear formal robes, burn incense, bow to the north, sit down in silence, and then recite and meditate on the _Xiaojing_. He even wrote a work called "Reciting and Meditating on the _Xiaojing_."

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The ritual that the _Xiaojing_ would sometimes be employed in was the Shidian 釋奠 (The Sacrifice for the First Teacher [Confucius]), which would take place at the Imperial University in the capital. After sacrificial offerings were made to Confucius, either the emperor or crown prince would lecture on one of the classics, fairly often the text would be the _Xiaojing_. Besides the academy's scholars and students, it is not exactly clear how many officials took part in the ceremony, but it was probably many.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 1

Notes: For small rituals, we usually just read of one participant.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The large Shidian ritual took place once a year. However, the small rituals in which people might recite the text to avoid illness or bad luck might have taken place daily or weekly.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: At the Shidian sacrifice, libations would have been offered to the representations of Confucius and his disciples. The human participants would have also probably consumed some of the ale libations.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, since the Shidian 釋奠 (The Sacrifice for the First Teacher [Confucius]) was an offering, a portion of the libations and offerings would be consumed by the ritual's participants.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: A fourteenth-century scholar named Song Lian (1310-1381) noted that the *Xiaojing* was the most frequently illustrated Confucian Classic. There are records of illustrated versions of the text going all the way back to the fourth century CE. Unfortunately, none of these early versions survive. Our earliest surviving illustrated *Xiaojing* was done on silk by the famous artist Li Gonglin 李公麟 (ca. 1041-1106). There still survives nine complete or partial sets of *Xiaojing* illustrations, which were completed from the 11th to the 18th centuries.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are two versions of the text, the Zheng Commentary on the New Text *Xiaojing* (今文孝經鄭注) and the Kong Anguo 孔安國 Commentary of the Old Text *Xiaojing* (古文孝經孔注). The former has 18 chapters, the latter 22. The Kong Anguo Old Text version has a chapter that does not appear in the New Text *Xiaojing*. The Old Text version adds these additional 24 characters: "Inside the smaller doors leading to the inner apartments are to be found all (the rules of government). There is awe for the father, and also for the elder brother. Wife and children, servants and concubines are like common people, serfs, and underlings" 子曰，閨門之內，具禮矣乎。嚴親嚴兄。妻子臣妾，繇百姓徒役也。James Legge, *The Hsiao Ching*, p.488.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, which version is better is based on age. The New Text *Xiaojing* was only created during the Western Han (202 BCE - 9 CE); however, the Old Text *Xiaojing* is supposedly pre-Han. However, proponents of the New Text version have repeatedly argued that the Old Text version is a later forgery; thus, it postdates the New Text version.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The Old Text version has 22 chapters rather than the New Text's 18 and the Old Text's Guimen 閨門 chapter doesn't exist in the New Text version.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

Notes: Indicative of the text's political significance, there were frequent debates about which version, the New Text or the Old Text Xiaojing, was the better one. Oftentimes these debates were of such importance that they occurred at court. During the Western Han, Emperor Cheng 漢成帝 (r. 32 -7 BCE) ordered Liu Xiang 劉向 to compare the two texts. Liu Xiang favored the New Text. In 719, Emperor Xuanzong (r.712-756) ordered an inquiry into which commentary on the texts was better: the Zheng Commentary on the New Text Xiaojing (今文孝經鄭注, supposed authored by the famous scholar Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 (127-200), or Kong Anguo's 孔安國 (c. 156-c.74 BCE) Commentary on the Old Text Xiaojing 古文孝經孔注. The renowned historian Liu Zhiji 劉知几 (661-721) claimed that Zheng Xuan did not write the Zheng commentary. Sima Zhen 司馬貞, on the other hand, attacked the authenticity of the Kong Anguo Commentary. Not satisfied with the results of the debate, Emperor Xuanzong ordered that the New Text version should be preferred, but that the Old Text version should continue to be studied. Xuanzong's own commentary on the New Text Xiaojing replaced that of the Zheng Commentary. He also ordered that his own commentary be set in stone. After the Tang Dynasty, both the Zheng and the Kong Anguo commentaries were lost (the Kong commentary was later reintroduced by Japanese scholars in the eighteenth century), but the Old Text Xiaojing survived in the Imperial Library and continued to excite scholarly interest and incite debate. The famous Song scholar and politician Sima Guang 司馬光 (1009-1086) wrote a work on the Old Text Xiaojing that claimed it was in many ways superior to the New Text Xiaojing. The great Neo-Confucian synthesizer, Zhu Xi 朱熹 (1130-1200) wrote a book called the *Xiaojing Expurgated* in which he favored the Old Text version and stated that only the first six chapters were the original text; the remaining twelve were merely commentaries that were most likely written by Han scholars. During the Yuan (1235-1368), one of the period's greatest scholars, Wu Cheng 吳澄 (1247-1331) wrote a work on the text confirming the superiority of the New Text version. Qing scholars continued this debate. The famous evidentiary scholars Cui Shu 崔述 (1740-1816) and Ruan Yuan 阮元 (1764-1849) both dismissed as a forgery Liu Xuan's 劉炫 (c. 546-c.613), Kong Commentary on the Old Text Xiaojing, which was re-introduced from Japan.

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

Notes: In cases in which the emperor initiated the debate, he would ultimately decide which text was superior. In other cases, the authority to decide is given to a famous Confucian statesman.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Scholars who argued in favor of the Old Text Xiaojing would contend that it was a true Warring States text (481-221 BCE). Hence, it was older than the New Text *Xiaojing*, which only came to light after the Qin First Emperor's bibliocaust and the founding of the Western Han (206 BCE - 9 CE). However, many advocates of the New Text Xiaojing would argue that the Kong Anguo Commentary on the Old Text Xiaojing was a forgery, which was only fabricated in early medieval (220-589) times.

↳ Content of text?

– No

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the *Xiaojing* was often seen as part of the Confucian canon. The earliest canon was the core classics are known as the Five Classics (the *Wujing* 五經): Book of Poetry *Shijing* 詩經, the Book of Changes *Yijing* 易經, the Record of Rituals (*Li ji* 禮記), and the Spring and Autumn Annals (*Chunqiu* 春秋). However, by the Eastern Han (25-220), both the *Analects* (*Lunyu* 論語) and the *Xiaojing* were incorporated into the canon to make the Seven Classics (*Qijing* 七經). During the Tang, this number was raised to twelve, and by the Song, there were thirteen classics. After the Western Han, the *Xiaojing* was always considered to be part of the Confucian Canon.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: The Confucian Canon was created in 136 BCE when the Martial Emperor of the Han (Han Wudi [r. 141-87 BCE]) established the Imperial University in the capital. He set up five texts to be studied each headed by an Erudite (*boshi* 博士: these are the Spring and Autumn Annals (*Chunqiu* 春秋), Book of Change (*Yijing* 易經), Book of Documents (*Shujing* 書經 or *Shangshu* 尚書), Book of Poetry (*Shijing* 詩經), and the Records of Rituals (*Liji* 禮記). These texts were selected because of their antiquity and because they had already been studied intensively in the form of commentaries. Later texts were added to the canon because they too became subjects of study at the Imperial University. By the Tang and Song period, a number of commentaries on the classics became part of the Canon.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, see note to previous question.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

Notes: From the Han through the Song (960-1279), the Confucian Canon merely kept growing in size. However, after the Song, the importance of the Thirteen Classics were eclipsed by the canonical works of Neo-Confucianism, which were called the Four Books (*Sishu* 四書), which were the *Analects* (*Lunyu* 論語), the *Mencius* 孟子, the *Great Learning* (*Daxue* 大學), and the *Doctrine of the Mean* (*Zhongyong* 中庸). From the Southern Song (1127-1279) to the late Ming (1368-1644), the *Xiaojing* lost most of its political importance.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Before it became scripture, literati viewed it as Confucian literature.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: This book had religious implications because its author sets forth filial piety as a metaphysical principle that can affect the entire cosmos. Nevertheless, its primary focus is on how people should act towards their parents, ancestors, and the state.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: Absolutely, the purpose of the book is to make its reader a more filial son and a loyal subject of the state. Indeed, it argues that one should transform the filial piety one exhibits towards parent into loyalty for his ruler. In other words, it is not enough to just serve your family, you must also serve the state.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Confucian literature

Notes: Long before it officially was deemed a Confucian scripture, it was viewed as a work of the Confucian school. In imperial China, it was seen as a work that had a strong imprint left by Confucius himself. Some believed that he created the text. Other scholars believed that his student, Zengzi, or Zengzi's disciples directly recorded Confucius' speech. So, the first two real books that students learned, the Analects and the Xiaojing, were books that recorded Confucius' direct speech.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– No

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Esoteric ritual

Notes: In Chapter Nine, "The Rule of Sages" (Shengzhi zhang 聖治章," when Zengzi asks Confucius about how do sages rule, Confucius replies, "No behavior is greater than filial piety. In terms of filiality, nothing is more importance than showing respect to one's father. In respecting

one's father, nothing is greater than making him a companion of Heaven (Tian 天). The one who did this was the Duke of Zhou. In the past, when performing the Suburban Sacrifice, he made Houji 後稷 (the Zhou ancestor) the companion of Heaven. When the Duke of Zhou performed the ancestral sacrifices in the Bright Hall, he made King Wen of the Zhou the companion of the High Deity (Shangdi 上帝)." The family that the text mentions is the Zhou family that established the idyllic Western Zhou (1049-771) polity. The family that rulers should emulate is the Zhou. Early Confucians viewed the Duke of Zhou as one of the founders of Confucianism. Hence, in early medieval texts, Confucians are called followers of the "Duke of Zhou and Confucius."

Does the text express a formal legal code?

— No

Notes: Chapter 11, "The Five Punishments Chapter" (Wuxing 五刑章) mentions a law code that has five punishments for 3,000 crimes. However, the worst offence is unfiliality. However, this is all it says about the formal legal code.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

— No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

— Yes

Notes: The *Xiaojing* posits that the body is entombed in the grave, but that the ancestor's spirit (guishen 鬼神) is worshipped in the ancestral temple. So there is a clear distinction between the spirit and the body.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

— Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

— Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

— Yes

Notes: Yes because people of the time thought there were more than one soul. The classical formulation is that each person has a hun 魂 (cloudy or yang soul) and a po 魄 (earthly or white soul). At death, the hun soul would wander above ground and hopefully ascend to Heaven. The po soul would sink into the Earth. It might go to the underground Yellow Springs (huangquan 黄泉), or remain in the grave. It was the hun soul that would receive sacrifices in the ancestral temple, whereas the po soul would make use of the grave goods interred with the body. In short, it was commonly thought that the body in the tomb was not without a spirit present. The hun soul can also be equated with spirit (shen 神) and the po soul with ghost/demon (gui 鬼).

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

— I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: In this text no. But, with the coming of Buddhism to China, a number of Confucians argued that with death, one's spirit came to an end as well. Daoist proponents of austere burials (bozang 薄葬) also believed that no spirit was attached to the body, so that it did not matter how the corpse was interred.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they did. But, at the same time, they believed in the existence of at least two souls, the hun 魂 that would wander above ground after the body's death, and the po 魄 soul that would probably stay with the corpse within the tomb,

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: The mainstream position was that, at death the cloudy hun 魂 soul would be released from the body and travel above ground, eventually making its way to the heavens. The body and the earthly po 魄 soul would be entombed in the grave. Zhuangzi 莊子 and Daoist-minded advocates of "austere burials" (bozang 薄葬) argued that the physical remains of the person had no consciousness; thus, it did not matter what happened to the body after death; i.e., no po soul was present. During the medieval period (220-907), some Confucians argued that one's consciousness disappeared with our death. In other words, our spirit was attached to our body; hence, once the body was inanimate, so was our spirit. Both of these positions were only held by a minority of scholars.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The text tells us that the mourner prognosticates about the location of the grave. The mourners peacefully lay [the body] to rest there. On behalf of the [departed's spirit], they place it [its spirit tablet] in the ancestral temple in order to satiate the spirit with food. The mourners also perform sacrifices in the Spring and Fall to think [of the dead] periodically. So, the spatial places described are the grave and the ancestral temple.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit or ghost (gui 鬼) of the deceased is fed sacrifices at the ancestral temple, but the assumption is that it is floating around above the surface of the Earth.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: The body of the deceased is put below the ground in the grave. It was typically thought that with the physical body there was a separate soul known as the earthly (po 魄) soul.

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Notes: Concerning burial, the "Mourning Parents Chapter" (Sangqin zhang 喪親章) states, "On behalf of them, make an inner and outer coffins and (burial) clothing and lift the [corpse] into the coffin. Display the ritual food vessels [before the coffin], which moves [the mourners] to grieve. Beat the chest and stamp your feet; use sorrow to escort them to the grave. Select the gravesite through prognostication, and place it there to rest in peace."

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

↳ Personal effects?

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

Notes: The text states that the grave goods should be displayed before the coffin. What it says about specific graves are a fu (a bronze tureen 簠) and a gui 簋 (a bronze bowl-shaped vessel used for holding grains). Since bronze was the most precious metals in early China, there were clearly valuable items. These two particular items also are used to signify other bronze eating and drinking vessels that would have been interred with the deceased.

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– Yes

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: The clothing for the dead could be considered another grave good.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify, but during the imperial period, bodies were usually interred in family cemeteries.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify, but during the imperial period, bodies, particularly couples, were buried in a family tomb-crypt.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: The mourner does not eat for three days after the parent's death. He must wail, wear rough (hemp) clothes, refrain from eating good food, listening to music, and having sex for three years.

Notes: Concerning the funeral, the "Mourning Parents Chapter" (Sangqin zhang 喪親章) states, "The mourner wails, but not uncontrollably. When performing the rites, he pays little attention to his appearance. His speech is not refined; he is uncomfortable in wearing beautiful clothes. When he hears music, he is not merry; when he tastes delicious food, it is not savory. This is the situation of one experiencing grief. For three days (after his parent's death), he does not eat. [By not prolonging this amount of time], he teaches the people to not use death to harm the living. He becomes emaciated but he doesn't harm his nature. These are the rules of the sages. The mourning should not last more than three years. This shows the people that everything [even grief] has its end. On behalf of the [deceased parent], make an inner and outer coffins and (burial) clothing. Then lift the [corpse] into the coffin. Display the ritual food vessels [before the coffin], which moves [the mourners] to grieve. Beat the chest and stamp your feet; use sorrow to escort [the deceased parent] to the grave. "

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: No. Most of the mourning actions seem to take place at the mourner's home. It is only after the initial part of the funeral takes place (the three days of fasting, the encoffining, and display of grave goods) that the body is taken to the burial ground.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the "Sagely Rule Chapter" (Shengzhi zhang 聖治章), we are told that the highest form of filiality is to make one's father a companion of the high god Heaven (Tian 天). We are told there that in the Suburban Sacrifice, the Duke of Zhou make his ancestor, Houji 後稷 into a companion of Heaven, and in the Bright Hall, he made his brother, King Wen of the Zhou, into the companion of the High Emperor (Shangdi 上帝). Tian and Shangdi were viewed as the supreme high gods.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: No, but the king's ancestors are. This is indicated by the Duke of Zhou making his ancestor Hou Ji a companion of Heaven, and his brother, King Wen, a companion of the High God (Shangdi).

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– Yes

Notes: Yes, since the king worships his ancestors as companions of the high gods, he must also share at least partly in their divinity.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– Yes

Notes: Since the Duke of Zhou's ancestors are companions to the high gods, I would think the answer is yes.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: The high gods will react benevolently to the king and his people if they are filial.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: None

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - I don't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

Notes: The *Xiaojing* does not make it clear. What it does make known is that, if one is perfectly filial, then disasters will not happen. It would seem that the displeasure of the high deities would have a connection to catastrophes occurring.

- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes

Notes: Although the *Xiaojing* does not make clear what spirits cause disasters and disruptions, it is clear that the spirits, including the high gods take pleasure in filiality. When the king and his people are filial, then the spirits, including the high gods, will make good things happen on earth.

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes

Notes: Although the *Xiaojing* does not make clear what spirits cause disasters and disruptions, it is clear that they, including the high gods dislike unfiliality. When the king and his people are unfilial, then the spirits, including the high gods, will make bad things happen on earth.

- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: None
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - Yes

Notes: The high gods communicate to the filial through omens and events. If a ruler and his people are filial, the high gods show their approval by creating peaceful conditions and prevent catastrophes from happening. If the king and his people are unfilial, then the world is in strife and disasterous things occur.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: By stating that, by perfecting filiality and brotherliness, one can communicate with the intelligent spirits (shenming 神明), the text does indicate that one can connect with the high gods.

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not clearly state that the spirits can be seen.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not clearly state that the spirits can be physically felt.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: The spirits primarily know whether their descendants are honoring and them and providing sacrifices.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: I don't know.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The *_Xiaojing_* does not say it directly, but it seems to indirectly suggest that if dead ancestors are treated well, then they will cause everything to fall into place. In the chapter entitled "Ruling through Filiality (Xiaozhi zhang 孝治章, it notes that, if the state and family are managed by means of filiality, then "while alive parents will be pacified, and when dead their spirits will be feasted with sacrifices. Therefore, all-under-Heaven will be peaceful, the living will not be harmed, and catatrophes will not occur." Hence, it seems that by means of filiality dead parents are pacified and do not cause trouble.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

Notes: In the "Ruling through Filiality Chapter" (Xiaozhi zhang 孝治章), we are told that, if we treat our parents well while they are alive, and provide them with sacrifices after they are dead, then there will be peace and bad things won't happen. This suggests that human spirits are pleased by filial piety.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

Notes: In the "Ruling through Filiality Chapter" (Xiaozhi zhang 孝治章), we are told that, if we treat our parents well while they are alive, and provide them with sacrifices after they are dead, then there will be peace and bad things won't happen. It implies if they are not treated filiality, then they will bring about disorder and disasters. So, obviously, unfiliality displeases them.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– Yes

Notes: In the Xiaojing, it is not clear how this communication takes place. What we do know is that perfect filiality will affect spiritual entities and cause them to respond. The text doesn't make clear, though, how the spirits will communicate with humans. The "Resonance chapter" (Ganying zhang 感應章) tells us, " If reverence is displayed in the ancestral temple, one does not forget his parents. If one cultivates his person and acts cautiously, then he will fear insulting his ancestors. If one displays reverence in the ancestral temple, then the ghosts and gods will appear. When filiality and brotherliness reach perfection, they communicate with the intelligent spirits, illuminate the Four Seas, and penetrate everything."

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– Yes

Notes: The passage from the "Resonance chapter" (Ganying zhang 感應章) is specifically

talking about the actions of enlightened kings (mingwang 明王), so the author seems to expect that the person who will cause a reaction from the spirits through his perfect filiality and brotherliness is the king.

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: Through omens and events

Notes: As noted previously, if people are filial, then the spirits express their delight by making sure good things happen and peace prevails. If people are unfilial, then the spirits express their displeasure by making catastrophes occur.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: It is a simple hierarchy of Heaven (Tian 天) and the High Deity (Shangdi 上帝) on top with ancestors and spirits (guishen 鬼神) below.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: Field doesn't know.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– Yes

↳ Libations?
– Yes

↳ Food?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Sacred objects?
– No

↳ Daily life objects?
– No

↳ Other?
– Specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: In the "Practice of Filial Piety Chapter" (Ji xiaoxing 紀孝行), we are told that "If you are a subordinate but act insubordinately, then you will be punished.... even if you daily use the three sacrificial meats to nurture your parents, you will still be unfilial."

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural beings care about how you treat and interact with others.

Notes: One should treat others well. Should not be arrogant, disobedient, or contentious. The "Son of Heaven chapter" (Tianzi zhang 天子章) tells us, "One who loves his parents, does not dare to do evil to others; one who respects his parents, does not dare slight others." In the "Practice of Filial Piety Chapter" (Ji xiaoxing 紀孝行), we are told that, "When serving your parents, if you are a superior but you should not be arrogant; when a subordinate, you should not create chaos; and when among commoners, you should not contend with others commoners. If you are a superior and are arrogant, you will lose your position; if you are a subordinate but act insubordinately, then you will be punished; if you are among commoners and are contentious, this will lead to weapons being drawn. Even if you daily use the three sacrificial meats to nurture your parents, you will still be unfilial."

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not say so directly. But if the ruler and/or people are filial, then bad things do not happen and calamity does not occur. Thus, the text implies that supernatural entities will punish the unfilial.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: Yes because much of the text is devoted to ritual actions that convey filial piety. For example, if one doesn't mourn correctly or provide sacrifices to one's deceased parents, of course the spirits will be angry.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: Of course, the most important group norm is to be filial to your parents.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Other
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– Yes

↳ Political failure?
– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?
– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
– No

↳ Sickness or illness?
– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?
– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
– Yes

↳ Other?
– Specify: None.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural rewards are given because people fulfill their general and specific filial duties. Their are distinct filial duties for the Son of Heaven (Tianzi 天子), the feudal lords (Zhuhou 諸侯), high ministers (Qingdafu 卿大夫), lower officials (shi 士), and commoners (shu 庶人). There are also general duties, such as respectfully caring for living parents, and grievously mourning dead ones.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god
– No

Notes: We do not know whether the rewards only come from the high gods. They could also come from ancestors.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: None

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Needless to say, the text puts a great deal of stress on filial piety's importance, to the extent that its first chapter states, "Filial piety is the root of virtue; it is from which our teachings are created."

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: The text puts an extraordinary emphasis on loyalty. Loyalty is born out of filiality; indeed, one must be loyal to be truly filial. Chapter one, "Kaizong Mingyi" (開宗明義), "Filiality begins with serving parents, then one serves his lord, and finishes by establishing a reputation." One of the central purposes of the text is to deny there is any conflict between being filial to your parents, and being loyal to the state.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes

Notes: Other virtues that the text mentions are brotherliness (ti 悌), music (yue 樂), propriety (li 禮). The "Broadening the Essential Way Chapter" (Guang Yaodao zhang 廣要道章) states, "For teaching the people to love and hold dear others, nothing is better than filiality. To change the social atmosphere and transform customs, nothing is better than music. To placate superiors and govern the people, nothing is better than propriety. Propriety means nothing other than to

respect."

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, when one mourns his parents, you have to forgo eating good food. That is because your grief won't allow you to enjoy it.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– Yes

Notes: During mourning you should decrease the amount of food you eat to the point where you become emaciated. However, you should not abstain from food to the point where it might endanger your health.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, during sacrifices one has to sacrifice animals and alcohol to nourish and delight the ancestors. Of course, these are items of worth. When burying one's parents, one buries them with

bronze vessels, which are of great value.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: When mourning your parents, you need to sacrifice three years of your time. During that time, you cannot eat fine food, listen to music, engage in sex, wear fine clothes, etc. Ancestral sacrifices also require time and fasting.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The small-scale rituals would include mourning for deceased parents and performing periodic ancestral sacrifices to them.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: For the mourning rites, since they would have to be performed whenever a close relative idea, we have no idea how often they were performed or the intervals between them. As for the ancestral sacrifices, they were supposed to occur four times a year, at the start of each season.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the reader's status. The nobles, the Son of Heaven, Feudal Lords, high officers, and low officers would all be expected to participate in large-scale sacrifices at the ancestral temple. Not the commoners, though.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?
– Yes
Notes: Alcohol drinking would have been a part of these rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?
– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?
– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?
– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?
– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?
– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the Suburban Sacrifice, the Sacrifice at the Illuminated Hall (Mingtang 明堂), and sacrifices at the ancestral temple.

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?
– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?
– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
– Yes
Notes: Foodstuffs

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
– Yes
Notes: When burying one's parents, one must put material offerings in the tomb, such as bronze ritual vessels, chariots, weapons, and foodstuffs.

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
– I don't know

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
– Yes
Notes: Sacrificial animals had to be without blemish; in other words, perfect.

↳ Other?
– Specify: None

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
– Yes

↳ By the community?
– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?
– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: We do not know who wrote the text or where. However, we do know that it was produced during the late Warring States period (481-221 BCE). During that time, what later became China was divided into seven territorial states. The text was created in one of these states.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: Even though the text was created in one of the seven polities that existed in the Warring States period, the *Xiaojing* only became important once the Han empire was created in 202 BCE. Within that empire and subsequent ones, both the state and a group of learned men known as Ru (Confucians) controlled the transmission and distribution of the text.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: During the imperial period of Chinese history (221 BCE-1911 CE), the only time the text was destroyed was during the Qin Dynasty (221 - 206 BCE). This is because the First Emperor of the Qin decreed that books privately held had to be destroyed.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: However, the text does hint that a good ruler should look after the elderly and infirm. The "Ruling through Filiality Chapter" (Xiaozhi zhang 孝治章), states, "The one ruling the country does not dare insult widows and widowers. How much less would he do so to low officers and the people? It is by this means that he obtains the favor of commoners." This implies that a ruler will only be loved by ordinary people if he takes care of the less fortunate.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: After learning the fundamentals of reading through the study of primers, the *Xiaojing* was one of the first texts a student would read. Hence, from the Han through the Song, the *Xiaojing* was commonly taught at elementary schools. During this same period, it was also one of the texts that had to be memorized to take the imperial civil service examinations. So, its study would have also been promoted at imperial universities as well. When the famous Neo-Confucian synthesizer, Zhu Xi (1130-1200) began learning the *Xiaojing* at school, he reportedly stated, "If one does not behave like [what is taught in the book], then he is not a human being" (See Thomas Lee, *Education in Traditional China: A History*, Leiden: Brill, 2000, p. 380).

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not explicitly state that it is only meant for males, but it assumes that its audience is male.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Texts such as this were meant for a male audience, but already by the Han Dynasty (202 BCE - 220 CE), there were works produced specifically for women. By the Tang Dynasty (618-906), a version of the *Xiaojing* was created for women. It was called the "Classic of Filial Piety for Women" (Nu Xiaojing 女孝經). Already during the Han Dynasty, women were reading the *Xiaojing* and often taught it to their children.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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